

NOVAFOODIES KEY FIGURES

28
Partners

6,587,345.00€
Total Budget

5,999,998.63€
EU Contribution

36 Months
(01.05.2023 – 30.04.2026)
Duration

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Coordinator:
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NOVAFOODIES PARTNERSHIP

Bringing together partners from Europe, Israel and China, with complementary backgrounds.

Demonstration of innovative functional food production systems based on a more sustainable value chain of marine and freshwater raw materials, such as macro/micro algae and different fish species, for conscientious European consumers

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 101084180.

NOVAFOODIES BACKGROUND

NOVAFOODIES is a unique consortium that connects organizations from Europe, Israel and China to investigate on innovative profitable and environmentally sustainable strategies for seafood production, as products derived from aquaculture and fisheries have remained static in recent decades. In order to create more balanced and effective aquatic food production systems, a comprehensive and ecosystems-based redefinition of primary processes and value chain is needed, in light of the growing population.

NOVAFOODIES will also work for boosting consumers' trust, investigating products traceability, and monitoring environmental impacts of productions, while demonstrating greater value chain sustainability to stakeholders by standardization activities too. **Algae**, which have great quality and nutritional value for humans, is one of the raw materials that will be studied for making the seafood value chain more sustainable: their production also contributes to mitigating climate change by CO₂ capture.

NOVAFOODIES GENERAL OBJECTIVES

NOVAFOODIES aims at providing consumers with new functional products of marine and freshwater origin, both for aquafeed and human consumption, using more sustainable production processes, without compromising sectoral competitiveness. The Consortium will work on the valorization of waste and fish biomass for a more circular and sustainable approach. In addition, NOVAFOODIES will also improve workforce skills, through the elaboration of training handbooks, online courses, and workshops.

NOVAFOODIES SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- ♣ Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture with 7 case studies in Europe, Israel, and China.
- ♣ Cultivation of macroalgae in earthen ponds and in liquid waste for obtaining respectively high-value products and proteins.
- ♣ Demonstrating the microalgal commercial potential, providing Ireland with a pilot facility.
- ♣ Beach wrack conversion to invertebrate biomass for aquafeed.
- ♣ Macroalgae-based packaging material and valorization of fisheries discards into human food products.
- ♣ Logistics optimization and traceability systems to collect and monitor catch and aquaculture data.
- ♣ NOVAFOODIES marketplace platform and App for end-users.

